

Smart Fisherman Safety and Weather Intelligence System

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To Cite this Article

Gutta Sree lakshmi, Kuntam Sathvika, Kukkala Jothsna, Kondeboina Divyaja, Menda Rajesh & Nallamothu Surya (2025). Smart Fisherman Safety and Weather Intelligence System. International Journal for Modern Trends in Science and Technology, 11(04), 01-07. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15108951>

Article Info

Received: 02 March 2025; Accepted: 28 March 2025.; Published: 30 March 2025.

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KEYWORDS

GSM Module,
GPS Module,
Fishermen Tracking,
Arduino,
Environmental Sensors,
Alert system.

ABSTRACT

The Smart fisherman safety and weather intelligence system is an innovative solution designed to enhance the safety and efficiency of fishermen at sea. The system integrates multiple technologies to monitor real-time weather conditions, provide location tracking, and issue SMS and CALL alerts during emergencies. The system utilizes Arduino as its core controller, interfacing with GPS modules, GSM modules, and various environmental sensors such as temperature, humidity, pressure and fire sensors. The system updates weather parameters continuously, providing real time insights into sea conditions, including temperature, wind speed, and atmospheric pressure. The GPS module tracks the precise location of the fishing vessel, ensuring that fishermen can navigate efficiently and avoid restricted or hazardous zones and in addition to these we added panic button and a buzzer for emergency alerts.

1. INTRODUCTION

Fisheries are extremely important to the international economy, offering jobs and food security to millions of individuals. Despite this, the occupation involves great risks, including unstable weather patterns, poor navigation, and potential entry into prohibited or dangerous areas. Fishermen rarely have access to real-time weather and tracking information, which makes them susceptible to storms, waves, and currents. These issues underscore the necessity of a sophisticated

safety and intelligence system that can track environmental conditions and guide fishermen safely. The Smart Fisherman Safety and Weather Intelligence System Using Arduino is intended to improve maritime safety through real-time weather monitoring, GPS tracking, geofencing, and emergency alert systems. The system is designed around an Arduino microcontroller as the central unit, which works together with GPS and GSM modules and environmental sensors to gather data and analyze the same. Temperature, wind speed,

atmospheric pressure, and humidity are monitored continually, giving the fisherman immediate information about the conditions of the sea. With this, informed decisions can be made prior to fishing in open sea. A vital aspect of this system is GPS-based location tracking, through which fishermen can know their precise location at sea. Furthermore, geofencing technology is utilized to warn fishermen when they are nearing risky areas like international maritime boundaries, stormy regions, or environmentally sensitive areas. If a fisherman ventures into a prohibited area, the system automatically sends an SMS alert through the GSM module to emergency contacts or coastal officials. This prevents delays in intervention and avoids potential hazards. In addition to these features, the system has a panic button where fishermen can send distress signals when they are in danger. This functionality comes in handy during situations where one needs urgent assistance, for instance, boat malfunctions, accidents, or sudden weather conditions. The distress call is transmitted to pre-set emergency contacts, hence the prompt response to emergency situations.

1.1 Objectives:

- Real-Time Weather Monitoring – Track and update sea conditions in real-time, such as temperature, wind speed, and atmospheric pressure.
- GPS-Based Location Tracking – Deliver accurate location updates of fishing boats to enable safe navigation and avoid entry into restricted or dangerous areas.
- Emergency Alert System – Employ GSM modules to send SMS alerts to emergency contacts or coastal authorities when in distress.
- Safety Geofencing – Alert the fishermen when coming close to international borders or sensitive ecological areas.
- Integration with Cloud Services – Make use of Things speak Cloud to access and monitor data remotely
- Panic Button for Emergencies – Allow fishermen to send instant distress signals in the event of an emergency.

1.2 principles of the smart fisherman safety and weather intelligence system

1. Real-Time Monitoring Principle – The system continuously monitors and updates weather conditions like temperature, humidity, and atmospheric pressure, enabling fishermen to make rational decisions based on real-time conditions.

2. Geofencing and Navigation Principle – With GPS technology, the system monitors the position of fishing boats and alerts them when reaching prohibited areas, ensuring regulatory compliance and safety while at sea.

3. Emergency Response Principle – The integration of a panic button and GSM module enables sending immediate distress calls through SMS to emergency contacts, facilitating prompt rescue operations in times of distress.

4. Automation and Low Power Consumption Principle – The system runs automatically, with minimum manual intervention while keeping power consumption low to enable extended use at sea.

5. Cloud Integration and Remote Monitoring Principle – The data is uploaded into the Things speak cloud, enabling authorities, relatives, or monitoring agencies to remotely monitor vessel movements and weather in real time

6. Cost-Effectiveness and Scalability Principle – Built with Arduino and off-the-shelf modules, the system is still cost-effective and scalable in that it can be afforded by many fisherman while future developments and integration to large marine monitoring network is facilitated.

1.3 Process Involved

1. Data Collection – Environmental sensors (temperature, humidity, and pressure) are employed by the system to keep an eye on weather. GPS module monitors the location of the vessel.

2. Data Processing – The Arduino microcontroller collects data from sensors and processes it in real-time, evaluating weather conditions and vessel location.

3. Geofencing & Hazard Detection – The system continuously verifies the vessel's location against predetermined restricted or hazard zones. When the vessel enters one of these zones, an alert is activated.

4. Emergency Alert System – In case a fisherman is in distress, the system can send an SMS alert through the GSM module to pre-defined emergency numbers like coast guards or relatives.

5. User Interaction – Fishermen can trigger the panic button manually in times of distress to send alerts in an instant.

6. Cloud Integration & Remote Monitoring – The data is uploaded to the Things speak cloud, enabling

authorities or families to remotely monitor real-time weather conditions and vessel movement.

1.4 Operating Conditions:

- Power Supply Requirements – The system operates on a stable power source, such as a rechargeable battery or solar power system, to ensure uninterrupted functionality at sea.
- Environmental Conditions –Temperature Range: The sensors and Arduino board function optimally within -10°C to 50°C.
- Humidity: The system can withstand high humidity levels common in marine environments but should be water proofed to prevent damage. Wind & Pressure Variations: The sensors are calibrated to detect strong wind conditions and sudden pressure drops, which indicate approaching storms. Communication Network Availability-The GSM module requires a stable cellular network to send emergency SMS alerts. In remote areas with weak signals, an alternative communication method, such as satellite-based messaging, may be needed.
- GPS Signal Strength – The GPS module requires a clear sky view to accurately track the vessel's location.

Obstructions, such as dense cloud cover or high waves, may reduce accuracy.

- Geofencing & Alert System – The system must have predefined restricted zones programmed to ensure real-time geofencing alerts. Proper calibration is needed to avoid false alerts when navigating near safe boundaries.
- Cloud Connectivity (Optional) –To upload data to Things Speak Cloud, an internet connection via GSM or another network is required. If cloud access is unavailable, data logging can be done locally on the Arduino's memory for later retrieval.

1.5 materials & methods:

A. Arduino Uno R3

We have chosen the Arduino as microcontroller because it is low-cost, open-source libraries and less complex programming. Arduino Uno is a microcontroller board with ATmega32 built-in. There are 14 digital inputs/outputs pins inputs and 5 analog input pins. It is based on a 16 MHz crystal oscillator, a power Jack and a reset button. It has all that is required to support the microcontroller. It has 4/8/16/32K bytes of In-System Programmable Flash with Read-While-Write capabilities. The board is provided with 5 volts supply from the voltage regulator. The program is loaded with USB jack with suitable code required for project design. It communicates instructions to the Arduino

microcontroller via the computer program coded in sketch and lastly it is the microcontroller that operates the circuit or device with more than one circuit by performing the specific commands.

B. GSM

GSM module is utilized for voice and data services which run at various frequency bands. GSM is an open, clockmaking cellular technology. The TDMA technique was employed to set the GSM technology as a clockmaking system for communication. The information is first minimized and converted into digits by a GSM prior to being transmitted, each in its own individual time slot. The digital system can transmit data at speeds between 64 kbps and 120 Mbps.

C. AT Commands

All operations in GSM are commanded using AT commands. The AT prefix is the command line's beginning and identifies the GSM modem.

D. GPS

A satellite navigation calculating technology that provides position and time information is the GPS.

Anyone with a GPS receiver and unobstructed view to at least four satellites of the GPS is welcome to use the system. With precise timing of the signals from GPS satellites, a GPS receiver calculates its position. GPS is now extensively applied and incorporated in smartphone devices. Navigation System with Time and Ranging (NAVSTAR) receiver has to receive information from a minimum of four satellites. The GPS receiver sends no data to the satellites. There are many applications, such as fleet management, taxis, and cell phones, that use this GPS receiver. With the help of specific RF frequencies, the small computers and antennas present in GPS modules directly receive data from satellites. From there, it will receive timestamps from all the visible satellites, along with other data. The module's antenna can know its position and time precisely if it can receive four or more satellites.

E. Liquid Crystal Display

A liquid crystal display (LCD), is a device that uses to display messages or data. It is a flat simple panel that exploits the nature of ambient light to project data. This is also called the modulation of light ability of liquid crystals. That implies that the liquid crystals the ability to produce light themselves for display purposes. They are dependent on light from the outside world. The

specific place in this document is indicated on the LCD. The location of the earth module using longitude and latitude of GPS tracking information. If we press button-I With GPS, we can easily trace the location of the person. And using GSM location will be sent to mobile. The functional pattern of the proposed system is illustrated in the above diagram (II, a). The block diagram illustrates how the components are connected to the system. We have utilized a power supply, Arduino R3, GPS, and GSM. The power supply is utilized to supply power to the system. The power supply is connected to the Arduino. GPS is interfaced with the Arduino, and Arduino is interfaced with GSM, whenever either of two buttons is pressed, GPS will send data to Arduino and from Arduino through GSM location information will be sent.

F. Things speak cloud

Things Speak cloud platform serves as a critical component of the Smart Fisherman Safety and Weather Intelligence System since it facilitates the collection of data in real time, remote observation, and visualization. The system employs an Arduino microcontroller for collecting environmental parameters from sensors in the form of temperature, humidity, atmospheric pressure, and the level of gas, as well as GPS coordinates for tracking positions. This information is then sent to Things Speak through a WiFi module (ESP8266) or GSM internet connectivity so that it can be stored and analyzed in the cloud.

b) methods:

1. Real-Time Data Collection Method

The system collects environmental data continuously through temperature, humidity, and pressure sensors. The GPS module monitors the current position of the vessel.

2. Data Processing and Analysis Method

The Arduino microcontroller analyzes sensor data and decides on weather conditions. It scans GPS coordinates to keep the vessel within safe areas.

3. Geofencing Technique

Restricted areas (like international waters or danger zones) are predefined and entered into the system. When the vessel goes into a restricted area, the system sends out an automatic warning.

4. Emergency Warning Technique

An SMS warning is sent using a GSM module in event of an emergency. A panic button is provided for fishermen to initiate distress signals manually for urgent assistance.

5. Cloud Data Storage and Monitoring Technique

The system sends real-time data to the Things speak cloud, allowing remote monitoring. Data from vessels can be accessed by authorities or relatives and quickly respond if necessary.

6. Low Power Consumption and Efficiency Technique

The system is made to efficiently use a low amount of power, which allows it to be used for prolonged fishing expeditions. Alternative sources of power such as batteries or solar panels may be employed to provide continuous operation.

2. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

The Smart fisherman safety and weather intelligence system is a cutting-edge innovation that aims to improve the efficiency and safety of fishermen on the water. The system brings together several technologies to track real-time weather, offer tracking of location, and send SMS notifications in case of emergency situations. The system uses Arduino as its central controller, communicating with GPS modules, GSM modules, and some environmental sensors like temperature, humidity, pressure sensors. The system continuously updates weather parameters for real-time sea conditions, including temperature, wind speed, and atmospheric pressure. The GPS module monitors the actual location of the fishing boat in order to let fishermen navigate well and steer clear of restricted or dangerous areas. Once the fisherman sails into a harmful area, be it high seas, storms, or areas blacklisted by government authorities, an SMS notification gets sent to predetermined emergency contacts or coastal surveillance centres via the GSM module. This project also supports geofencing to alert fishers when moving towards international shores or ecologically sensitive areas. The system provides real-time monitoring with low power usage and can be modified for use in larger marine monitoring networks. The solution is economical, scalable, and can be an important tool in providing the safety and sustainability of fishing operations. Along with these we included panic button for emergency notification.

Fig 1:Block diagram of Smart fisherman safety and weather intelligence system

2.1 Working principle of smart fisherman safety and weather intelligence system

The Smart Fisherman Weather and Safety Intelligence System functions through the integration of several sensors and communication modules to provide real-time monitoring and safety for seafarers. The system automatically gathers information from environmental sensors such as temperature, humidity, and pressure to observe weather patterns. A GPS module monitors the exact location of the boat, and a GSM module provides communication through sending warnings whenever needed. The Arduino microcontroller interprets all the incoming information, reading weather and location information in real-time. In the event that the ship navigates into a dangerous or prohibited area, the system activates the geofencing alert, alerting fishermen and automatically sending an SMS to emergency contacts, including coastal monitoring stations. There is also a panic button included so that fishermen can send alarm signals at once in times of emergencies. The system is also compatible with the Things speak cloud, which provides remote access and monitoring of data. With real-time weather forecasts, accurate navigation, and emergency alert systems, this system makes fishing

safer and more efficient while providing prompt responses to potential threats.

2.2 experimental setup procedure

the Smart Fisherman Safety and Weather Intelligence System, an experimental setup was created and tested in controlled and real-life conditions. The system was initially constructed with basic hardware components such as an Arduino microcontroller, a GPS module, a GSM module, and environmental sensors such as temperature, humidity, and pressure sensors. A panic button was incorporated to send emergency messages, and a power supply system in the form of batteries or solar panels was employed to facilitate continuous operation.

After the hardware installation was done, the circuitry connections were made, and the system was programmed with the Arduino IDE. The software had libraries for GPS tracking, GSM communication, and processing of sensor data. Geofencing boundaries were also defined in the code to check if the system could detect entry into forbidden or dangerous areas accurately. The system was subsequently tested in a controlled setting on land, where each component was validated. The GPS module was tested for precise location tracking, the GSM module was tested for successful SMS delivery, and sensor readings were cross-checked with standard meteorological equipment to validate accuracy.

Fig 2: experimental setup

After successful testing on land, the system was put to field test on water by mounting it on a fishing vessel. Motion was simulated towards prohibited areas to test the geofencing alert system for functionality. Real-time weather parameters were tracked and compared with

official weather updates to authenticate the sensor readings. Testing was also conducted on the panic button to ensure that the distress alerts were dispatched appropriately. For enhanced user convenience, the data of the system was uploaded onto the Thingspeak cloud, enabling remote monitoring and access.

Upon analyzing the results, appropriate modifications were incorporated to maximize sensor precision, GPS accuracy, and power consumption. The overall performance of the system was checked to ensure that it could endure marine environments and issue real-time safety warnings. The experimental setup effectively proved that the system could monitor weather conditions effectively, locate fishermen, and issue emergency warnings, thus being a viable means for improving safety in fishing activities.

3.RESULTS & DISCUSSION

The Smart Fisherman Weather and Safety Intelligence System Based on Arduino proved efficient real-time monitoring of weather and location tracking. The system effectively gathered and processed environmental information, such as temperature, humidity, and atmospheric pressure, to provide fishermen with precise information about sea conditions. The GPS module effectively tracked the location of the vessel, ensuring safe navigation and warning fishermen when entering restricted or dangerous areas. The geofencing functionality functioned as planned, sending warnings when the ship approached international boundaries or environmentally protected zones. In addition, the emergency alert function, such as the panic button, performed as expected by dispatching SMS to pre-programmed emergency contacts upon occurrence of a distress situation

Fig 3: IR sensors senses fire

The integration with the Things speak cloud allowed remote access to data, enabling authorities or family members to monitor fishermen's status in real time. Overall, the system proved to be a cost-effective and efficient solution for enhancing the safety and security of fishermen at sea.

The below image shows an LCD module displays sensor data, likely from a microcontroller-based system such as Arduino. Explanation of displayed value:

- T : Temperature (34°C)
- H : Humidity (53%)
- P: Pressure (1005.64HP) with normal atmospheric range at sea level which
- P: fisherman press panic button, 0 changes to 1

Fig 3: liquid crystal display

This photo depicts several alerts – "abnormal fisherman condition" This alert probably comes from a fisherman monitoring system that indicates abnormal vital signs like:

- abnormal temperature
- more or less humidity
- abnormal pressure
- fire or gas leakage

When fisherman is at sea, during that time in that boat it may be leakage of gas or fire, more humidity the sensors are talk to microcontroller, it will seconds call and SMS alert is sent the user number, by using SMS we can trace the fisherman using link in the message.

Fig 5: SMS from the fisherman

By using message when the rescue team press the link in the message, they can see the fisherman location

Fig 6: location of the fisherman using SMS link

Fig 7: Call from the fisherman

3.1 Thing Speak IOT analytics dashboards:

The Image shows Thing Speak IOT analytics dashboards monitoring patient health parameters over time, consists of different field charts:

Fig 8: temperature variations overtime

The graph illustrates temperature fluctuations captured in a fishermen tracking system across three different dates: March 9, March 16, and March 23. The x-axis is used to depict the date, while the y-axis is used to represent temperature values. The trend indicates a steady rise from March 9 to March 16, wherein the

temperature increases slightly above 35°C. But from March 16 onwards, the temperature drops back to approximately 30°C on March 23. There is a notable spike on March 23, where the temperature suddenly jumps to 50°C, reflecting an anomaly or an outlier fluctuation. The sudden spike may reflect an outlier because of a sensor malfunction or an unusual environmental factor.

Fig 8: humidity level over time

The picture displays a line graph labeled "fishermen tracking system," which plots humidity levels against time. Dates, namely March 9, March 16, and March 23, are on the x-axis, while humidity is on the y-axis, from 40 to 70. From the chart, there is an upward trend in humidity, with it beginning around 40 on March 9, going up to about 60 by March 16, and then higher to around 70 on March 23. The fact that there are many data points towards March 23 indicates repeated reading or fluctuations. This trend upwards suggests a sustained increase in humidity levels, which could be vital for fishermen to forecast weather, as high humidity can affect visibility, sea conditions, and overall safety while fishing.

Fig 9: fire activity fluctuations

The picture shows a line chart labeled "fishermen tracking system," which plots the trend of fire-related information over time. The x-axis is the date, and the major points are labeled as March 9, March 16, and March 23. The y-axis is fire intensity or events with

approximately 15 to more than 35. The graph illustrates a steep climb from about 15 on March 9 up to more than 35 on March 16, which reveals a dramatic increase in fire activity or intensity. After this climax, there's a steep decline, with various data points scattered around the 20-mark on March 16, indicating wobbles or double readings. By March 23, fire values have receded slightly but are still rather stable at levels around 20. This pattern indicates a landmark event or pinnacle fire activity approximately mid-March, followed by a slow tail-off. Data may be important for tracking fire risks, incendium processes, or ecosystem threats to fishers.

Fig 10: pressure variations overtime

The chart has a line chart title "fishermen tracking system". The chart displays pressure changes over time, with the x-axis having the title "Date" and marking three major points: March 9, March 16, and March 23. The y-axis, "pressure," has values ranging approximately from 1.01k. The red line on the chart indicates a decline from March 9 to March 16 to the lowest value of pressure on March 16, and a steep incline from March 16 to March 23. The chart indicates pressure fluctuations, which may be important in monitoring weather or environmental conditions influencing fishermen.

Fig 11: gas level trends

The image displays a line graph labeled "fishermen tracking system," illustrating the trend of gas levels over time. The date along the x-axis ranges from key points such as March 9 and March 16, while the y-axis

represents gas levels. The red line on the graph demarcates a consistent increase in the level of gas, from 0.00 on March 9 to a value above 15.0 on March 16. It indicates a consistent accumulation or increase in gas with time, which can be helpful in monitoring environmental parameters affecting fishermen, such as the use of fuel, gas production, or the concentration of air gas.

4. CONCLUSION

The IoT-based Fishermen Tracking System with Arduino is a new technology solution that is intended to improve the security, safety, and real-time monitoring of fishermen while they are on the sea. GPS, GSM, IoT, and different environmental sensors are used to integrate this system, which ensures continuous location tracking, weather conditions, and emergency alert provisions. The pressure sensor assists in anticipating bad weather, and the DHT11 sensor tracks temperature and humidity to offer environmental information. The fire sensor provides early detection of onboard fires to avoid serious accidents. The panic button and buzzer system also enable fishermen to transmit emergency distress signals, facilitating quick response from authorities or surrounding boats. With the use of IoT technology, this system provides a cost-efficient, scalable, and automated method for maritime safety. Not only does it facilitate monitoring of fishermen, but also mitigates risks of accidents by offering timely notifications and real-time messaging. The Arduino microcontroller, which processes the data and sends it to the IoT cloud platform, makes it possible for authorities and relatives to monitor the boat's status in real-time. This promotes a safe and efficient navigation system with fewer missing fishermen cases and better rescue services during emergencies.

5. FUTURE SCOPE

Future work on the fishermen tracking system can focus on collecting real-time data, providing predictive analytics, and integrating weather forecasts to make it more accurate and hazard-prone. A mobile app with dynamic visualizations and automatic alerts would make it more accessible and user-friendly. Moreover, integrating additional parameters such as wind speed and wave height would give a complete monitoring system for safer and more efficient fishing operations.

Conflict of interest statement

Authors declare that they do not have any conflict of interest.

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